

Ventilation Opportunities in Air Conditioning Systems

**Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO,
Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units,
Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv**

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

Version 1.1.1, 23 October 2025

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17423420

all versions DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17423419

Abstract

This work applies Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization programs (BESOO) to determine the energy conservation potential of ventilation when using air conditioning.

The default ventilation is 10 changes per hour, equivalent to 1,560 CFM per 100m² apartment.

Ventilation saves more than 70% of energy for cooling at 25°C-26°C in Jerusalem and 25% in Tel Aviv. When cooling at 26°C, ventilation reduces the Heat Index discomfort period by 99% (from 911 to 11 hours per year) in Jerusalem and 55% in Tel Aviv.

The default ventilation in this work was 10 changes per hour; however, after 4 changes per hour (600 CFM for a 100m² apartment), the impact of increased ventilation volume is very low.

When operating at the optimum comfort (OCAC) cooling temperature, the ventilation saves 74% of cooling hours in Jerusalem and 40% in Tel Aviv.

Glossary

Ave	average
CHI	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C (79.9°F)
dtau	time period of the integration = integration interval, sec
HI	temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by the air temperature and the air relative humidity (RH), °C, (°F)
HIC	Heat Index in the cooling hours, °C
HIO	Heat Index(HI) above Comfort Heat Index (CHI) not in cooling, °C
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning – setting of air conditioning thermostat that results in minimum air conditioning hours, minimum energy consumption, and a Heat Index below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C)
RH	relative humidity of air, %
Ta	ambient (outside) air temperature, °C
Tr	room air temperature, °C
TTC	Thermal Time Constant, hours

Energy Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Calculations and application of the Heat Index involve degrees Fahrenheit. Energy is expressed in Joule (J) or Watt-second (Ws) and kWh, and power in Watts.

Works related to air conditioning use many imperial units regardless of the default metric units, like:

- CFM – cubic feet per minute, air flow from the air conditioning distribution system

Heat Index – Air Humidity Temperature Equivalent

The Heat Index (HI) is the equivalent of discomfort temperature and humidity in the air, °C (or °F).

Following is the official definition of the Heat Index as on the NOAA site [4]:

“The Heat Index is a measure of how hot it really feels when relative humidity is factored in with the actual air temperature. To find the Heat Index temperature, look at the Heat Index Chart above or check our Heat Index Calculator. As an example, if the air temperature is 96°F and the relative humidity is 65%, the heat index--how hot it feels--is 121°F. The red area without numbers indicates extreme danger.

Since heat index values were devised for shady, light wind conditions, exposure to full sunshine can increase heat index values by up to 15°F. Also, strong winds, particularly with very hot, dry air, can be extremely hazardous”.

Heat Index online calculators:

- NOAA - National Weather Service [5]
- ISGlobal - The Barcelona Institute for Global Health [6]
- Calculator.net - Heat Index Calculator [8]

Heat Index, including calculation formulas, is described in detail in the publication [1].

Comfort Heat Index (CHI)

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is the Heat Index which is comfortable enough and does not waste energy for overcooling. Setting air conditioning systems to a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) will provide air conditioning that is comfortable enough for those suffering from heat and much better for those suffering from cold.

Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is described in detail in the publication [1].

Table 1 - Comfort Heat Index

Comfort Heat Index, °F	≤ 79.9
Comfort Heat Index, °C	≤ 26.6

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC)

Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC) refers to the thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Based on the analyzed data for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, the Heat Index remained below the Comfort Heat Index at cooling setpoints below 25.5°C in Jerusalem and 25.7°C in Tel Aviv.

This issue is described in detail in the publication [1].

Table 2 - Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), °C

OCAC for Jerusalem, °C	25.4
OCAC for Tel Aviv, °C	25.6

BESOO Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program

The BESOO simulation program is described in [1]. This work applies version 542, which is for cooling only, so the cooling period is in the whole period of the simulation (whole year – 365 days). The starting day of the simulation is on the coldest day. The coldest day in 2023 was 7-Feb (3.43°C) in Jerusalem and 14-Feb (10.60°C) in Tel Aviv.

The initial temperatures of the room air and the outside wall layers are set to the average ambient air temperature (T_a) on the first day of the simulation. On this day, the T_a temperature was corrected to the average daily temperature from midnight till the actual same temperature as the average daily temperature.

Table 3 - Initial temperatures in version 542

v542		Jerusalem	Tel Aviv
minimum average temperature day		07/02/23	14/02/23
day average temperature	°C	3.43	10.60
temperature at midnight	°C	2.8	6.80
minimum temperature	°C	1.9	2.90
hour of minimum temperature		4:20	7:20
hour of average temperature		11:10	10:10

Chart 1 - Average daily temperature – Jerusalem, °C

Chart 2 - Average daily temperature – Tel Aviv, °C

Chart 3 - Building and apartment

Table 4 - Example of version 542 input page for Jerusalem

choose direction of part 1:

choose direction of part 2:

Cool On temperature °C

infiltration - number of changes per hour V/hr

ventilation - number of changes per hour V/hr

activation of ventilation Δ (Troom - Ta) > °C

height between floors (outside) m

room height (inside) m

floor length of outside wall part 1 m

floor length of outside wall part 2 m

outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness m

outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness m

central layer (3) concrete thickness m

inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness m

inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness m

Table 5 - Example of version 542 results table for default input values in Jerusalem

21/10/2025 15:55:33 GMT			
nowagreen.com BESOO page 542Jm, v542Jm.01 Comfort Heat Index (CHI), unlimited cooling period thermostatic control			
CoolT	26		°C
URL	https://nowagreen.com/BESO/542Jm		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	109.61	hours	TTC
start day	20230207		
last day	20240206		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230517		
cooling end date	20231028		
cooling hours in the simulation period	773		9%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	288	kWh thermal	50%
quantity of condense during cooling	416	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	286	kWh thermal	50%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	574	kWh thermal	100%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	766	20230908	19:40
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	1227	20230729	18:20
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	1691	20230909	17:20
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.66	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	779	hours	9%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	28.19	20230813	20:10
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.92	20230728	11:20
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours	27.45	°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	11	hours	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.63	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	768	hours	9%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI	27.5	°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	3	hours	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	28.15	20230813	20:40
Ventilation			
ventilation hours	2503	hours	29%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	7987	hours	91%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	5484	hours	63%

Meteorological Data

The data sets for ambient air temperature, relative humidity (RH) and global solar radiation are from the Israel Meteorological Service website [2]. The records are for every 10 minutes. The data sets are for the years 2023 and 2024.

Global solar radiation is multiplied by a conversion factor according to the direction of the outer wall, month and hour.

The conversion factors are from the “*Hourly Solar Radiation at Selected Tilt Angles and Directions in Tel Aviv*” internet site [3].

Ventilation

The thermostat for cooling may be set in the range from 16°C to 30°C. To enable energy saving using ventilation also when the thermostat is set to 16°C, the ventilation limit is set in this work to the room air temperature above 13°C.

The default value for the difference between the room temperature and the ambient temperature to activate ventilation is 1°C. It can be changed on the input page, “*Activation of ventilation $\Delta (T_{room} - T_a) >$* ” field.

The default ventilation flow of 10 changes per hour may also be changed on the input page.

$$1 \text{ m}^3/\text{hr} = 0.5886 \text{ CFM}$$

Table 6 - CFM equivalent of ventilation changes per hour for the default apartment (100 m2)

Ventilation Changes/hr	CFM
1	156
2	312
3	468
4	624
5	780
6	936
7	1,092
8	1,248
9	1,404
10	1,560
11	1,716
12	1,872
13	2,028
14	2,184
15	2,340
16	2,496
17	2,652
18	2,808
19	2,963
20	3,119

Simulation Results

Table 7 - Version 542 results for cooling temperature 16°C-30°C in Jerusalem with and without ventilation (10 changes per hour)

Cool On °C	ECW [kWh/y]			hrC [hr/y]			hrHICup [hr/y]		
	V10	V0	V10/V0	V10	V0	V10/V0	V10	V0	V10/V0
16	7,997	9,052	-12%	5,469	7,324	-25%	0	0	N/A
17	7,260	8,340	-13%	5,070	6,882	-26%	0	0	N/A
18	6,483	7,652	-15%	4,675	6,434	-27%	0	0	N/A
19	5,683	6,978	-19%	4,246	6,065	-30%	0	0	N/A
20	4,804	6,327	-24%	3,787	5,666	-33%	0	0	N/A
21	3,789	5,701	-34%	3,251	5,425	-40%	0	0	N/A
22	2,847	5,073	-44%	2,677	5,102	-48%	0	0	N/A
23	2,070	4,456	-54%	2,098	4,752	-56%	0	0	N/A
24	1,448	3,855	-62%	1,600	4,393	-64%	0	0	N/A
25	963	3,273	-71%	1,147	4,000	-71%	0	0	N/A
26	574	2,720	-79%	773	3,597	-79%	11	914	-99%
27	314	2,205	-86%	466	3,183	-85%	226	2,580	-91%
28	159	1,722	-91%	276	2,780	-90%	276	2,778	-90%
29	69	1,269	-95%	164	2,245	-93%	166	2,245	-93%
30	19	892	-98%	71	1,656	-96%	72	1,656	-96%
Ave			-53%			-58%			-94%

Cool On thermostat setting of cooling temperature, °C
 V10 ventilation -10 changes per hour
 V0 no ventilation
 ECW thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh thermal/year
 hrC hours of cooling/year
 hrHICup [hr/y] hours when the room temperature is above the CHI
 CHI Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C (79.9°F)

Table 8 - Version 542 results for cooling temperature 16°C-30°C in Tel Aviv with and without ventilation (10 changes per hour)

Cool On °C	ECW [kWh/y]			hrC [hr/y]			hrHICup [hr/y]		
	V10	V0	V10/V0	V10	V0	V10/V0	V10	V0	V10/V0
16	12,200	12,842	-5%	6,702	8,088	-17%	0	0	N/A
17	11,337	12,029	-6%	6,306	7,740	-19%	0	0	N/A
18	10,461	11,206	-7%	5,894	7,394	-20%	0	0	N/A
19	9,573	10,376	-8%	5,443	7,010	-22%	0	0	N/A
20	8,712	9,548	-9%	5,016	6,622	-24%	0	0	N/A
21	7,864	8,721	-10%	4,598	6,218	-26%	0	0	N/A
22	7,006	7,909	-11%	4,176	5,797	-28%	0	0	N/A
23	6,138	7,122	-14%	3,748	5,352	-30%	0	0	N/A
24	5,308	6,361	-17%	3,339	4,985	-33%	0	0	N/A
25	4,496	5,607	-20%	2,926	4,662	-37%	0	0	N/A
26	3,662	4,864	-25%	2,456	4,262	-42%	616	1,378	-55%
27	2,880	4,143	-30%	1,986	3,867	-49%	1,965	3,819	-49%
28	2,175	3,451	-37%	1,536	3,408	-55%	1,549	3,408	-55%
29	1,528	2,797	-45%	1,112	2,981	-63%	1,124	2,981	-62%
30	1,005	2,190	-54%	761	2,499	-70%	771	2,501	-69%
Ave			-20%			-36%			-58%

Table 9 - Ventilation changes per hour, and cooling energy and duration for OCAC=25.4°C in Jerusalem

vent V/hr	ECW		hrC		hrHICup hr/y
	kWhth/y	V/V0	hr/y	V/V0	
0	3,048	0%	3,847	0%	0
1	1,514	-50%	1,962	-49%	0
2	1,134	-63%	1,439	-63%	0
3	986	-68%	1,224	-68%	0
4	911	-70%	1,122	-71%	0
5	868	-72%	1,068	-72%	0
6	841	-72%	1,037	-73%	0
7	824	-73%	1,016	-74%	0
8	813	-73%	1,005	-74%	0
9	805	-74%	997	-74%	0
10	800	-74%	991	-74%	0
20	790	-74%	980	-75%	0

OCAC Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning – setting of air conditioning thermostat that results in minimum air conditioning hours, minimum energy consumption, and in Heat Index below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C)

vent, V/hr ventilation, number of changes per hour

ECW energy for cooling and condense, kWh thermal/year

hrC cooling hours, hr/y

hrHICup hours when Heat Index is above the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C), for OCAC should be 0

Chart 4 - Energy consumption at OCAC temperature in Jerusalem (25.4°C), kWh thermal/year

Table 10 - Ventilation changes per hour, and cooling energy and duration for OCAC=25.6°C in Tel Aviv

vent V/hr	ECW		hrC		hrHICup hr/y
	kWhth/y	V/V0	hr/y	V/V0	
0	5,158	0%	4,427	0%	0
1	4,364	-15%	3,267	-26%	0
2	4,141	-20%	2,933	-34%	0
3	4,050	-21%	2,776	-37%	0
4	4,012	-22%	2,698	-39%	0
5	3,997	-23%	2,660	-40%	0
6	3,992	-23%	2,649	-40%	0
7	3,990	-23%	2,647	-40%	0
8	3,990	-23%	2,647	-40%	0
9	3,989	-23%	2,646	-40%	0
10	3,989	-23%	2,646	-40%	0
20	3,988	-23%	2,645	-40%	0

Chart 5 - Energy consumption at OCAC temperature in Tel Aviv (25.6°C), kWh thermal/year

References

1. Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17375074
<https://nowagreen.com/BESO/542Jm>
<https://nowagreen.com/BESO/542TA>
2. Israel Meteorological Service
<https://ims.gov.il>
3. Dataset: Hourly Solar Radiation at Tilt Angle and Direction in Tel Aviv – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.12804970
<https://nowagreen.com/se>
4. NOAA - National Weather Service – Heat Forecast Tools – Heat Index
<https://www.weather.gov/safety/heat-tools>

* * *